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Cytokine storm in COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

COVID-19-associated cytokine storm is associated with higher risk for fatal outcome. It is characterized by increased IL-2, IL-7, granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, interferon- γ inducible protein 10, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α , and tumor necrosis factor- α . Predictors of fatality are elevated ferritin and IL-6.

CYTOKINE STORM

Cytokine release syndrome (CRS) or cytokine storm syndrome (CSS) is a form of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) that can be triggered by a variety of factors such as infections and certain drugs¹.

It occurs when large numbers of white blood cells are activated and release inflammatory cytokines, which in turn activate yet more white blood cells (the vicious cycle).

CRS is also an adverse effect of some of monoclonal antibody drugs, as well as adoptive T-cell therapies^{2,3}.

Severe cases have been called cytokine storms⁴. When occurring as a result of drug administration, it is also known as an infusion reaction⁵.

Symptoms include fever, fatigue, loss of appetite, muscle and joint pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, rashes, fast breathing, rapid heartbeat, low blood pressure, seizures, headache, confusion, delirium, hallucinations, tremor and loss of coordination. Laboratory tests and clinical monitoring show low blood oxygen, widened pulse pressure, increased cardiac output (early), potentially diminished cardiac output (late), high levels of nitrogen compounds in the blood, elevated D-dimer, elevated transaminases, factor I deficiency and excessive bleeding, higher-than-normal level of bilirubin^{2,6}.

Accumulating evidence suggest that a subgroup of patients with severe COVID-19 might have a cytokine storm syndrome⁷.

Secondary haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (sHLH) is an under-recognized, hyperinflammatory syndrome characterized by a fulminant and fatal hypercytokinaemia with multiorgan

failure. In adults, it is most commonly triggered by viral infections⁸.

Cardinal features of sHLH include unremitting fever, cytopenias, and hyperferritinaemia; pulmonary involvement (including ARDS) occurs in approximately 50% of patients⁹.

A cytokine profile resembling sHLH is associated with COVID-19 disease severity, characterized by increased interleukin (IL)-2, IL-7, granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, interferon- γ inducible protein 10, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α , and tumor necrosis factor- α ¹⁰.

Predictors of fatality from a recent retrospective, multicenter study of 150 confirmed COVID-19 cases in Wuhan, China, included elevated ferritin and IL-6, suggesting that mortality might be due to virally driven hyperinflammation¹¹.

IMMUNOSUPPRESSION AND IMMUNOMODULATION

Corticosteroids are not routinely recommended and might exacerbate COVID-19-associated lung injury¹².

Immunosuppression is likely to be beneficial. Re-analysis of data from a phase 3 randomized controlled trial of IL-1 blockade (anakinra) in sepsis, showed significant survival benefit in patients with hyperinflammation, without increased adverse events¹³.

A multicenter, randomized controlled trial of tocilizumab (IL-6) receptor blockade, licensed for CRS, has been approved in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia and elevated IL-6 in China¹⁴.

Janus kinase (JAK) inhibition could affect both inflammation and cellular viral entry in COVID-19¹⁵.

Therapeutic options for COVID-19-associated cytokine storm include steroids (not routinely recommended), intravenous immunoglobulin, selective cytokine blockade (anakinra, tocilizumab) and JAK inhibition (baricitinib⁷).

Medicinal plants with immunomodulatory effect¹⁶ might also be considered as potential additional treatment or as a source of immunomodulatory drugs derived from such plants:

1. *Hydrastis canadensis* L. root (goldenseal root): reduces plasma TNF- α , INF- γ and NO levels, inhibits the T helper-type 2 cytokine profile.

2. *Momordica charantia* L. fruits and seeds (bitter melon): inhibits the release of TNF- α , NO and proliferation of spleen cells induced by PHA and Con A.

3. *Nigella sativa* L. seeds (black cumin): reduces pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cell (PDA) synthesis of monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), TNF- α , IL-1 β and cyclooxygenase (COX)-2, inhibits the polymorphonuclear leukocytes functions.

4. *Allium sativum* L. fruits (garlic): suppress leukocyte inflammatory cytokine production.

5. *Boerhaavia diffusa* L. root (punarnava): inhibits human NK cell cytotoxicity *in vitro*, inhibits production of NO, IL-2 and TNF- α .

6. *Urtica dioica* L. aerial parts (common nettle): reduction of TNF- α and other inflammatory cytokines by inhibiting the genetic transcription factor.

Some medicinal plants and their active compounds are reported to inhibit monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP-1): wogonin (Wog) from *Scutellaria baicalensis* radix (Chinese skullcap),

tetramethylpyrazine from the rhizome of the *Rhizoma Chuanxiong*, curcumin from turmeric, and berberine from umbellatine. Compounds that are reported to inhibit TNF- α or protect the tissues from TNF- α -induced injury are paeonol from Cortex Moutan, Tanshinone IIA (Tan IIA) from danshen and catalpol from *Rehmannia glutinosa* (Chinese foxglove¹⁷).

Various natural products from traditional Chinese medicine have been shown to safely suppress proinflammatory pathways and control inflammation-associated disease¹⁸.

Amirghofran and coworkers investigated the NO modulatory activity of the extracts of several medicinal plants native to Iran including *Dracocephalum kotschyi*, *Linum persicum*, *Dionysia termeana*, *Salvia mirzayanii*, *Ferulago angulata* and *Euphorbia cheiradenia*, and concluded that results indicate the presence of anti-inflammatory and macrophage inhibitory substances in these plants¹⁹.

CONCLUSION

COVID-19-associated cytokine storm is associated with higher risk for fatal outcome. It is characterized by increased IL-2, IL-7, granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, interferon- γ inducible protein 10, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α , and tumor necrosis factor- α . Predictors of fatality are elevated ferritin and IL-6.

Therapeutic options for COVID-19-associated cytokine storm include steroids (not routinely recommended), intravenous immunoglobulin, selective cytokine blockade (anakinra, tocilizumab) and JAK inhibition (baricitinib).

Medicinal plants and their active compounds, such as curcumin, berberine, wogonin, etc. that have been reported to lower the cytokine production, might also be potential immunomodulatory agents for the treatment of cytokine storm, but further research is needed.

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